

RDM og FAIR kursustilbud på de danske universiteter (2022)

Undervisningstilbud kan kategoriseres i:

- FAIR / Forskningsdata management
- GDPR / Informationssikkerhed
- Forskningsintegritet / Etik
- Data Science
- Andet (relateret til forskningslivcyklus)

Specifikke kurser i "FAIR / Forskningsdata management" tilbydes som regel af universitetsbibliotekerne eller forskerstøttefunktioner. Kurserne er hovedsagelig målrettet Ph.d.-studerende og fokuserer bl.a. på Data Management Planer. Enkelte undervisningstilbud indlejrer FAIR forskningsdata management i det større Open Science perspektiv med en bredere målgruppe, der omfatter f.eks. også forskningsstøtteenhederne.

- *Handlingspunkt: Der bør indtænkes stærkere kobling til fagspecifikke tilbud.*

Kurser vedrørende "GDPR / Informationssikkerhed" tilbydes oftest som korte online moduler. De er obligatoriske for alle ansatte.

- *Handlingspunkt: Der bør være mere fokus på betingelser og udfordringer for åbne forskningsdata (accessibility). Her bør der inddrages DPO'er, CISO'er og juridisk ekspertise.*

Kurser i "Forskningsintegritet / Etik" er som regel obligatoriske for alle Ph.d.-studerende og nyansatte forskere og tilbydes på de enkelte fakulteter (hvis der er flere). Her indgår der i de fleste tilfælde også en introduktion til (FAIR) forskningsdata management. Der synes særlig fokus på udfordringerne inden for sundhedsvidenskabelig forskning.

- *Handlingspunkt: Der bør defineres læringsmål som minimumskrav for obligatoriske kurser for Ph.d.-studerende, vejledere og nyansatte forskere, såsom kendskab til FAIR vokabulariet og DMP konceptet (f.eks. jf. FAIR4HE Knowledge Units KU3.01.01, KU3.01.02, KU3.01.03, KU3.01.05, KU3.01.07 og KU3.01.08).*

"Data Science" dækker meget bredt over forskellige emner relateret til f.eks. programmering, HPC og statistiske metoder.

- *Handlingspunkt: Der bør overvejes mulige koblinger til FAIR data management (i samarbejde med data labs, e-science centre e.l.).*

"Andet" omfatter f.eks. informationssøgning, referencehåndtering og introduktion til videnskabeligt arbejde. Her vises de kun som (vel etablerede) eksempler på, hvordan ikke-fagspecifikke emner formidles.

Overordnede anbefalinger

- Revidér og tilpas FAIR4HE Learning Outcomes for hhv. Bachelor-, Master- og Ph.D.-niveau og tilføj to nye niveauer: 'Professionals' og 'Research Support'.
- Sammenlign læringsmål med politikker på de enkelte universiteter for at definere minimumskrav (f.eks. udarbejdelse og brug af DMP'er).
- Publicér kompetencemodellen og læringsmål i en let brugbar og overskuelig form.
- Udbred kendskab til kompetencemodellen og læringsmål til undervisere på universiteterne for integration i eksisterende, fagspecifikke kurser for studerende (Bachelor og Master).
- Brug kompetencemodellen og læringsmål til at tilpasse eksisterende kurser og etablere nye kurser.

Name	Institution	Level	Type	Duration	Description	Comments
Responsible Conduct of Research	UCPH	PhD	mandatory	full day	4 modules (SUND/SCIENCE): 1) Scientific Misconduct and Good Scientific Practice 2) Authorship 3) Research Data Management 4) Conflicts of Interest	offered by the individual faculties
GDPR online course	UCPH	everyone	mandatory	60 minutes		
Introduction Course for New PhD Students	UCPH	PhD	optional (2 ECTS)	4 days	various topics including: - Career Planning - Academic Writing - Stress Management - Collaboration	offered by the Department of Science Education
Open up your Academic Publishing Toolbox	UCPH	PhD	optional (0.5 ECTS)	full day	4 modules: 1) Introduction to FAIR Research Data Management 2) Copyright in Publishing 3) Open Access Publishing 4) Responsible Metrics - Quantitative Evaluation of Researchers	offered by Copenhagen University Library, Department for Research Support
Digital Literacy	UCPH	BA			collection of various courses and modules within 5 areas: 1) Data Management 2) Digital Analysis and Methodology 3) Digital Reflection 4) Technological Understanding 5) Digital Scientific Literature	to be implemented at the individual faculties
Data Management Plan Workshop for Horizon grant holders	UCPH	VIP/TAP	optional	half day	Open Research Data in Horizon Data Management Plans FAIR Principles	offered to PostDocs, project coordinators and research support staff
Literature Management	ITU	PhD	optional (0.5 ECTS per module)	full day (each module)	3 modules: 1) Academic information seeking and reference management 2) Literature reviews: planning and searching for evidence 3) Researcher's rights to scientific works and Anti-plagiarism screening	offered by The Royal Danish Library additional modules expected in 2023
Research Code of Conduct	ITU	PhD	(1 ECTS)	2 days	GDPR, IT Security, Data Security Conflicts of Interest Plagiarism Authorship Open Access	
Introduction to research integrity and research ethics	RUC	PhD	mandatory (1 ECTS)	full day		offered by the Unit of Academic Development
Research data management and the FAIR principles in Open Science	RUC	PhD	mandatory (0.5 ECTS)	half day		offered by the Unit of Academic Development and Roskilde University Library
Nvivo basic/advanced	RUC	PhD/VIP	optional (0.5 ECTS for both courses combined)	2 half days	Nvivo basic: - plan and create a project - perform basic coding in text documents - perform simple queries Nvivo advanced: - perform coding in various data types (text, survey data, images, audio, video) - look for patterns across data - create simple visualizations	offered by the Unit of Academic Development and Roskilde University Library
Introduction to data science in Python	RUC	VIP		half day		offered by the Unit of Academic Development
Statistics and Data Science using Python	RUC	PhD	Data science theory and hands-on: 3.5 ECTS Data science project 1.5 ECTS Participating in both 5 ECTS in total	9 half days	Exploratory data analysis Data cleaning and Tidying Data Classification and clustering Analysis and Interpretation Natural Language Processing (NLP) Deep Learning	offered by Centre for Big Data, Roskilde Doctoral Schools and the Unit of Academic Development

Python / R	RUC	VIP	optional		Python R	offered by the Unit of Academic Development
Introduction for PhD students	RUC	PhD		2 days		offered by Roskilde Doctoral Schools
GDPR	RUC	VIP	mandatory			offered by DPO for each department
How to find Open Access research data	RUC	BA		120 minutes		offered by the Department of Social Sciences and Business and Roskilde University Library
E-learning course: Research Integrity at Aarhus University	AU	VIP	mandatory	60 minutes	The course consists of two mandatory modules: 1. Responsible Research Conduct 2. Irresponsible Research Practices In addition, you have access to eleven optional supplementary modules. 3. Planning Your Research 4. Managing and Recording Your Research 5. Data Selection, Analysis and Presentation 6. Scholarly Publication 7. Professional Responsibilities 8. Communication, Social Responsibility and Impact 9. Conflicts of Interest 10. Research Involving Human Participants 11. The Care and Use of Animal in Research 12. Intellectual Property 13. Export Controls	
Introduction to managing Research Data, FAIR principles, and Open Access	AU	PhD/VIP	optional (0.2 ECTS)	half day	Research Data Management Data Management Plans FAIR Principles Open Access Pathways	offered by the Graduate School of Health and Aarhus University Library
Introduction to research data management	AU	PhD	mandatory		(part of the introduction day for new PhD students)	offered by the Graduate Schools of Natural and Technical Sciences and Aarhus University Library
Data Management Workshop	AU	PhD	mandatory		(part of the research integrity course for PhD students)	offered by the Graduate Schools of Natural and Technical Sciences and Aarhus University Library
Data management workshop for Horizon 2020 grant holders	AU	VIP				offered by the Research Support Office and Aarhus University Library
Introduction to data management	AU	VIP				offered by the individual departments and Aarhus University Library
Data Management in Citizen Science	AU	BA/MA				
Datamanagement & Stata	AU	PhD	optional (0.6 ECTS)	2 days	Handling Research Data and Legal Aspects Data Documentation REDCap and Stata Transparency and Reproducibility	offered by the Graduate School of Health
Introduction to Quantitative Research Methodology	AU	PhD	optional (5 ECTS)	4 days	Research Design Literature Review Data Quality Data Analysis Data Management	offered by the Graduate School of Business and Social Sciences
Online Course in Web Archives and Web Archiving	AU	all	optional (3 ECTS)	5 days	technical characteristics of archived web, existing web archives, archiving services, and how to do their own web archiving	offered by DIGHUMLAB

Data management plan and responsible handling of research data	SDU	PhD	optional (4 ECTS)	3 days	Graduate programme: Clinical Research - create a data management plan for your PhD project - give insights into how data management supports research projects - understanding current principles and standards for documentation of quantitative data - provide considerations and instruments to carry through data documentation and data control of research data from raw data to datasets for analysis - understand and apply in practice the general rules of appropriate data management in accordance with responsible conduct of research	offered by the Graduate School, Faculty of Health Sciences
Responsible Conduct of Research	SDU	PhD	Mandatory (2 ECTS)	2 days	Customized courses for the TEK, NAT, HUM, SAMF, SUND faculties. The course consists of four modules: • Module 1: Academia and Responsible Conduct of Research • Module 2: Laws and regulations • Module 3: Research Data Management (including FAIR) • Module 4: Publication, authorship, and peer reviewing	offered by the University Library of Southern Denmark
Love your data	AAU	PhD	1 ECTS	2 days	Course introducing data management and data management planning	Offered by the university library // CLAAUDIA
Responsible Code of Conduct	AAU	PhD	1 ECTS	1 day	General introduction to the Danish Code of Conduct. Includes 1,25 hours on data management	Offered by an academic group. Participation by the library // CLAAUDIA
GDPR online course	AAU	all	Mandatory	Around 1-2 hours (elearning)	General introduction to GDPR	Information security
Responsible Code of Conduct	AAU	SUND special edition	Mandatory (no ects)	1-2 hours	General introduction to staff at SUND at AAU about the focus at good scientific work, including data management planning.	
Introduction to responsible conduct of research and research data management for new employees	DTU	VIP	mandatory	4 hours	- Research planning and conduct - Publications and communication - Authorship - Collaborative Research and IPR - Conflicts of Interest - How breaches of responsible conduct of Research are handled - Research data management and the FAIR principles	Introduction to responsible conduct of research is a mandatory course for all new employees at DTU working in relation to research.
Webinar Series on Research Data Management	DTU	everyone		20 minutes each	- Introduction to the data life cycle - Get started with DMPOnline - the FAIR principles as basis for your data management plan - Publication of code & software - legal - Use HPC - High Performance Computing - in your data workflows - Publish your data in DTU data - Costs of research data management - Tips for the pre-award process - Open Science expectations in Horizon Europe	Courses are optional if not part of a course provided by a department. Introductory level for researchers, PhD students and support staff.
Introduction to Research Data Management for PhD Students	CBS	PhD	Mandatory (no ECTS)	1 hour online self-study + 1 hour assignments (among others production of a data flow chart) + 2 hours classroom teaching	- Introduction to RDM based on PhD students wishes and interests (surveyed before class) - Data lifecycle, RDM practices throughout the data lifecycle, FAIR data - DM planning on the basis of the submitted data flow charts - Introduction to DMPonline and DMP templates	Offered by the RDM Support/ CBS Library
Introduction to Research Data Management for Social Scientists (RDM I)	CBS	all		90 minutes	Data lifecycle RDM practices throughout the Data lifecycle DM planning (brief intro) FAIR Data (brief intro)	Offered by the RDM Support/ CBS Library
How to Write a DMP (RDM II)	CBS	all		90 minutes	Comparison of 3 example DMPs and their strengths and weaknesses DM Planning with and without DMPonline	Offered by the RDM Support/ CBS Library
How to Make your Research Data FAIR (RDM III)	CBS	all		90 minutes	What do the FAIR principles entail? How can you make your data FAIR?	Offered by the RDM Support/ CBS Library
GDPR online course	CBS	all	mandatory	Around 1-2 hours (elearning)	General introduction to GDPR	

FAIR / Research Data Management
GDPR / Information Security
Research Integrity / Ethics
Data Science
Other

FAIR / Research Data Management
GDPR / Information Security
Research Integrity / Ethics
Data Science
Other